

Metal Ion-biomolecule Systems. I. Polarographic Studies on the Binary and Ternary Lead(II) Complexes of Citrulline and 5'-Inosine Monophosphate

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Our interest¹ of investigating metal ion interactions with biologically significant ligands prompted us to take up the present work in which both the binary and ternary Pb^{II}-IMP-Cit systems have been studied by polarographic technique under identical conditions (37°, *I* = 0.15 mol dm⁻³ (KNO₃), pH 6.0). No mention of either system was found in the literature.

Results and Discussion

Binary systems : The stability constants of binary complexes of Pb^{II} with amino acid Cit and nucleotide IMP were determined separately under identical conditions used for the ternary systems. Excess ligand concentration with respect to that of the metal ion was always maintained. The reduction of the metal ion, both in the presence and in the absence of ligands (AA or nucleotide), was found to be reversible and diffusion-controlled. Gradual increase in ligand concentration shifted the *E*_{1/2} values of Pb^{II} to more negative potentials, indicating complex formation.

$\Delta E_{1/2}$ vs log [X] plots were non-linear, indicating stepwise complex formation with both the ligands. Therefore, DeFord and Hume's method² was used to obtain the overall stability constants of the binary complexes. Pertinent details and the *F*₀[X] values are given in Tables 1 and 2. The graphical extrapolation method of Leden³ was adopted to obtain β values. The curved *F*₀[X] plot, the linear *F*₁[X] plot and the constant *F*₂[X] values are consistent with two complexes being present in Pb^{II}-IMP system. Likewise, formation of three complexes are evidenced with Pb^{II}-Cit system. The values of overall stability constants are given in Table 4. Tables 1 and 2 also show a comparison of the experimental and calculated values of log *F*₀[X] which provides a useful check on the reliability of the adopted method.

TABLE 1 - POLAROGRAPHIC DATA FOR Pb^{II}-IMP SYSTEM

[Pb^{II}] = 0.2 mmol dm⁻³, *I* = 0.15 mol dm⁻³ (KNO₃), temp. = 310 K, pH = 6.0

[IMP] _T mmol dm ⁻³	$\Delta E_{1/2}$ mV	<i>F</i> ₀ [X]	<i>F</i> ₁ [X] 10 ⁻³	<i>F</i> ₂ [X] 10 ⁶	log <i>F</i> ₀ [X] Observed. (Calcd)*
0	0	1.000 0	—	—	—
0.5	30	4.262 4	6.525	—	0.629 6 (0.620 6)
1.0	35	8.504 7	7.505	2.254 7	0.929 6 (0.926 8)
1.5	40	13.841 2	8.561	2.207 2	1.141 2 (1.140 6)
2.0	41	20.127 8	9.565	2.157 5	1.303 7 (1.307 4)
3.0	43	37.518 0	12.173	2.307 6	1.574 2 (1.562 8)
4.0	44	59.137 3	14.535	2.321 2	1.771 8 (1.757 4)

*Calcd. from $F_0[X] = 1 + 5.25 \cdot 10^3 [IMP] + 2.2 \cdot 10^6 [IMP]^2$

Ternary system : For the mixed ligand system, the concentration of the weaker ligand (nucleotide) was kept constant while varying the stronger ligand (AA) concentration. The system was studied at two fixed [IMP] concentrations, viz., 1.0 and 1.5 mmol dm⁻³. A shift in half-wave potential to more negative values with increase in citrulline concentration was observed. As reductions were polarographically reversible, the Schaap and McMasters' method⁴ was used to evaluate the *F*₀₀ functions at constant ionic strength. The values of the function, *F*₀₀[X,Y], calculated directly from the half-wave potential and diffusion current constant values

TABLE 2 – POLAROGRAPHIC DATA FOR Pb^{II}-CIT SYSTEM

[Pb^{II}] = 0.2 mmol dm⁻³, I = 0.15 mol dm⁻³ (KNO₃), temp. = 310 K, pH 6.0

[Cit] _T mmol dm ⁻³	[Cit ⁻] mmol dm ⁻³	ΔE _{1/2} mV	F ₀ [X]	F ₁ [X] × 10 ⁻³	F ₂ [X] × 10 ⁻⁶	F ₃ [X] × 10 ⁻⁹	log F ₀ [X]	
							Observed	Calcd *
0	0.000 0	0	1.000 0	—	—	—	—	—
1 0	0.999 3	21	3.968 6	2.970 5	—	—	0.598 6	0.573 7
2 0	1.998 6	30	10.589 0	4.797 9	1.319 8	—	1.024 8	0.951 8
2 5	2.498 3	34	15.091 8	5.640 5	1.393 2	0.449 5	1 178 7	1.116 3
3.0	2.998 0	36	16.378 9	6.429 7	1.424 2	0.384 9	1.214 2	1.267 7
4 0	3.997 4	51	36.805 6	8.957 2	1.700 4	0.357 8	1.565 9	1.192 3
4 5	4.497 0	56	61.847 8	13.530 7	2.528 5	0.502 2	1.791 3	1.655 8

* Calcd. from : F₀[X] = 1 + 2.16 × 10³ [Cit] + 2.70 × 10⁵ [Cit]² + 3.20 × 10⁸ [Cit]³

are given in Table 3. It was found that only one mixed complex, [Pb(IMP)(Cit)], having log β₁₁₁ = 2.21, was formed. The stability of mixed ligand complexes can be compared with that of simple complexes, and the relative stability of ternary complexes can be quantitatively expressed in terms of Δ log K values. The Δ log K for the equilibrium,

was found to be -2.61. This suggested that 1 : 1 : 1 mixed ligand species was less stable than the simple 1 : 1 complexes (or the reaction from left to right was not favoured). In other words, IMP binds better to Pb²⁺ than to the binary Pb(Cit)⁺ complex. This is due to the fact that more coordination positions are available on Pb^{II} than on Pb(Cit)⁺ complex. The negative values of

Δ log K generally result from the absence of electronic effects or specific interactions between the two ligands in a ternary system. However, it should be noted that the negative values of Δ log K do not preclude the formation of the ternary complexes in solution.

Relative stability of a ternary complex with respect to the parent binary complexes can also be evaluated from the expression,

The mixing constant (K_m) is deduced from equation,

$$\log K_m = \log \beta_{111} - 1/2 [\log \beta_{102} + \log \beta_{120}]$$

and the stabilisation constant (K_s) from equation

$$\log K_s = \log K_m - \log 2 !$$

TABLE 3 – POLAROGRAPHIC DATA FOR Pb^{II}-IMP-CIT SYSTEM

[Pb^{II}] = 1.0 mmol dm⁻³, I = 0.15 mol dm⁻³ (KNO₃), temp. = 310 K, pH = 6.00

[Cit] _T mmol dm ⁻³	[IMP] _T mmol dm ⁻³		log (I _M /I _C)		F _∞ [X,Y]		F ₁₀ [X,Y] × 10 ⁻⁴	
	1.0(1)	1.5(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
	Δ E _{1/2} (mV)							
0 5	7 5	12.0	0.003 67	0.207 9	1.768 4	3.964 9	0.023 6	0 102 9
1 0	10.5	15.0	0.022 47	0.253 7	2.311 7	5.515 2	0.066 2	0.206 5
2 0	11.5	15.6	0.044 12	0.246 8	2.619 0	5 705 8	0.048 5	0 112 8
2.5	12.0	20.0	0.088 80	0.201 8	2.916 3	7.116 4	0.050 6	0.146 6
3 0	12.3	23.0	0.064 80	0.211 1	3.013 2	9.090 3	0 045 4	0.188 0

TABLE 4 – FORMATION CONSTANTS OF BINARY AND TERNARY COMPLEXES OF Pb^{II} $I = 0.15 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} (\text{KNO}_3)$, Temp. = 310 K, pH = 6.0

Species	$\log \beta$
Pb(IMP) ⁻	$\log \beta_{101} = 3.72$
Pb(IMP) ₂	$\log \beta_{102} = 6.34$
Pb(Cit) ⁻	$\log \beta_{100} = 3.33$
Pb(Cit) ₂	$\log \beta_{120} = 5.43$
Pb(Cit) ₃ ⁻	$\log \beta_{130} = 8.51$
Pb(IMP)(Cit)	$\log \beta_{111} = 2.21$

The values of K_m and K_s are found to be 0.0362 and 0.0181 respectively. These positive values show that the mixed complex is more stable than the simple 1 : 2 complexes.

Experimental

Solutions of lead nitrate (Qualigens), citrulline (Loba) and 5'-inosine monophosphate (S. D. Fine) were prepared in water (distilled twice in an all-glass still). Mercury (polarography, E. Merck) was used in the dropping mercury electrode. Solutions to be polarographed contained $5 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3} \text{ Pb}^{\text{II}}$ and 0.001 % Triton

X-100 (as maximum suppressor) at a constant ionic strength of $0.15 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} (\text{KNO}_3)$.

Polarograms were recorded with a Systronic polarograph. The dropping mercury electrode had a droptime of 2 s at an effective height of 48 cm Hg. Purified nitrogen gas (passed successively through alkaline pyrogallol, chromous chloride and solvent water) was used to deoxygenate the solutions. pH was measured with an Elico LI-122 pH meter equipped with a standard glass-calomel combination electrode

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References

1. KABIR-UD-DIN and I. A. KHAN, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1978, **109**, 1343; Z. KHATOON and KABIR-UD-DIN, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1989, **14**, 34; 1990, **15**, 217; *Polyhedron*, 1990, **20**, 2437; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 344; 1992, **69**, 677
2. D. D. DEFORD and D. N. HUME, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5321.
3. I. LEDEN, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1960, **188**, 1941
4. W. B. SCHAAP and D. L. MCMASTERS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4699.

